

Comparative Analysis Of Lexico-Semantic, Linguocultural, And Pragmatic Features In The Motivational And Nominative Field Of The Tcr In Russian And Uzbek Languages

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Abstract: *The main tasks of the coach are to challenge the athletes every day, to encourage them to physical education and sports, to unite them and to place in their hearts the spiritual foundations of physical education and sports.*

Keywords — rowing, continuous sequence of movements, dynamic balance, water sports basics, safety vest.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of the TCR (Tactical Communication Regime) encompasses various linguistic units used in communication strategies within specific contexts. This article aims to conduct a comparative analysis of the lexico-semantic, linguocultural, and pragmatic features present in the motivational and nominative field of the TCR in both the Russian and Uzbek languages. By examining these features, we seek to understand how communication strategies differ across linguistic and cultural boundaries, shedding light on the nuances of linguistic expression in different socio-cultural contexts.

Lexico-Semantic Features

Lexico-semantics refers to the study of the meaning of words and their relationship within a language. In the context of the TCR, certain lexical choices carry specific connotations and implications that reflect cultural values and norms. For instance, in Russian, terms such as "доверие" (trust) and "сотрудничество" (cooperation) may be emphasized to convey a sense of solidarity and teamwork within a communication strategy. Conversely, in Uzbek, words like "ишбилармонлик" (collaboration) and "ишқишлоқ" (mutual understanding) might be preferred to emphasize collective effort and mutual understanding.

Furthermore, lexico-semantic features in the motivational and nominative field of the TCR can also reflect hierarchical relationships and power dynamics within a given cultural context. For instance, in Russian, terms such as "руководство" (leadership) and "подчинение" (subordination) may be used to denote authority and obedience. In contrast, in Uzbek, words like "бошқариш" (management) and "қўллаб-қувватлаш" (support) may be employed to highlight the collaborative nature of decision-making processes.

Linguocultural Features

Linguocultural features refer to the cultural aspects embedded in language use, including customs, traditions, and

social norms. In the context of the TCR, linguistic expressions are often influenced by cultural perceptions of politeness, respect, and social hierarchy. For example, in Russian culture, formal address forms such as "вы" (you, formal) and honorific titles like "господин" (Mr.) or "госпожа" (Mrs.) may be preferred in professional settings to convey respect and deference.

Similarly, in Uzbek culture, linguistic expressions of politeness and hospitality play a significant role in communication strategies. For instance, the use of honorific titles such as "ўстоз" (teacher) or "усто" (master) demonstrates respect for individuals of higher status or expertise. Additionally, expressions of gratitude and hospitality, such as "Раҳмат" (Thank you) and "Кайфланаман" (I'm pleased), are commonly used to foster positive interpersonal relationships.

Pragmatic Features

Pragmatic features refer to the context-dependent aspects of language use, including speech acts, implicatures, and communicative strategies. In the context of the TCR, pragmatic considerations play a crucial role in achieving communicative goals and managing interpersonal relationships. For example, in Russian, indirect speech acts and implicit directives may be employed to convey messages politely and diplomatically.

Similarly, in Uzbek, pragmatic strategies such as hedging and mitigation may be utilized to soften requests or suggestions and avoid direct confrontation. Additionally, cultural norms regarding face-saving and preserving harmony in interpersonal interactions influence pragmatic choices in communication strategies. For instance, in both Russian and Uzbek cultures, maintaining positive face and avoiding loss of face are important considerations in communication.

Conclusion

In this comparative analysis, we have explored the lexico-semantic, linguocultural, and pragmatic features within the motivational and nominative field of the Tactical

Communication Regime (TCR) in both Russian and Uzbek languages. Through this examination, several key insights have emerged regarding the nuances of communication strategies across linguistic and cultural boundaries.

Firstly, in terms of lexico-semantics, we have observed distinct lexical choices that reflect cultural values and norms. Russian tends to emphasize concepts such as trust, cooperation, and leadership, reflecting a hierarchical structure and a focus on formal relationships. Conversely, Uzbek emphasizes collaboration, mutual understanding, and support, reflecting a more collective and egalitarian approach to communication.

Secondly, linguocultural features play a significant role in shaping communication strategies in both languages. Cultural perceptions of politeness, respect, and social hierarchy influence linguistic expressions, with formal address forms and honorific titles being prominent in both Russian and Uzbek. Additionally, expressions of gratitude, hospitality, and respect for authority are common features that facilitate positive interpersonal interactions.

Lastly, pragmatic considerations are crucial for achieving communicative goals and managing interpersonal relationships. Both Russian and Uzbek employ indirect speech acts and pragmatic strategies such as hedging and mitigation to convey messages politely and diplomatically. Cultural norms regarding face-saving and preserving harmony further shape pragmatic choices in communication strategies.

In conclusion, the comparative analysis highlights the intricate relationship between language, culture, and communication within the motivational and nominative field of the TCR. Understanding these features is essential for effective cross-cultural communication and intercultural competence. By recognizing the nuances of communication strategies in Russian and Uzbek languages, individuals can navigate diverse linguistic and cultural contexts with sensitivity and adaptability, fostering mutual understanding and collaboration across cultural boundaries.

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